

USE OF MULTIMEDIA IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE.

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ELSEVIER

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Abstract: The need to introduce innovative educational technologies in order to increase the effectiveness of the educational process is becoming relevant. The use of innovative computer technologies is manifested not only as a way of obtaining knowledge, but also as a means of forming professional competencies. A number of modern methods of teaching a foreign language are distinguished and detailed information is given about the tasks of web search technology. The authors come to the conclusion about the feasibility of using web quests as one of the types of innovative technologies in the educational process, the effectiveness of their use is confirmed by the growth of cognitive activity of students in foreign languages, the possibility of personalizing the educational process, increasing the level of socialization of future specialists, the level of formation

Keywords: method, English, samara, talim, O^Qiyon, Foreign Language Act.

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Introduction

We are aware that in the same year, at a videoselector meeting under the chairmanship of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, dedicated to improving the system of teaching foreign languages, the requirement for Foreign Language teachers to have a national and international certificate has been introduced since 2021. And this imposes a huge responsibility on the shoulders of our Foreign Language teachers. Now we need to organize the course process based on interactive methods using a new Act instead of traditional lesson techniques. This training is also a requirement of the period, when the teacher has to work even more on himself. Paying attention to new methods of teaching in the article, first of all, it is worth paying attention to the type and effect of these methods Separately, it should be noted that new methods and requirements have been developed in our republic in accordance with the recommendations of the pan-European framework for teaching a foreign language, assessing the knowledge and skills of Foreign Language teachers (CEFR). According to him, textbooks are being created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, the classrooms were equipped with stands and new information communicative techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language also increased day by day. Foreign Language Science was divided into four aspects (reading, yoish, listening, understanding and speaking), each of which was given separate concepts and skills.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most effective. In the process, including:

- when using computers, the reader can also hear video rollers, shows, dialogues in a foreign language, watching movies or cartoons;
- foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs can be heard and watched;
- the use of tape recorders and cassettes, which is considered a much more traditional method;
- CD players can be used. The use of these techniques ensures that the process of students learning a foreign language is more intense and efficient.

In the process of passing foreign language lessons, it is necessary to use advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative-informational means.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Advanced techniques serve as a compass in the thorough mastery of a foreign language.

One such technique is the use of role-playing games in the course of the lesson. Role-playing games are the application of various situations in our real life in the process of learning a foreign language. This technique will help create a language environment in the course process.

For example: In Case 1, old virgins accidentally meet. Situation 2 crosses a road without crossing a child who does not follow the rule of the road while passing the road. Case 3. In the store enters the buyer to get food. 4 stage performances are performed on these situations. Such life role-playing games create an atmosphere of language in the course process, give students the opportunity to freely express their thoughts. In the process of participating in role-playing games, students learn to think, learn to freely express their emotional state in a foreign language. In the process of preparing for role-playing games, they correct each other's lexical, grammatical and pronunciation errors. Making mistakes and correcting this mistake will also help you learn the language and teach students the correct pronunciation. The use of role-playing games in the course process ensures that at the same time all students are actively involved in the lesson. In addition, role-playing games increase students' interest in learning a foreign language and create a lively, cheerful atmosphere to the course process. This will serve to increase the effectiveness of foreign language lessons.

The next method is English, which is "Keys-stadi" ("case" – a specific situation, phenomenon, "study" – learn, analyze) is a method aimed at conducting training based on the study, analysis of specific situations.

One of the most interesting techniques - in the game "pantomime" is divided into 3 groups. One person from each group is taken out on the board. Different words are given to them on the basis of the list. They must explain the words to the rest of the group members through gestures, actions without saying a word.

"Problem situation solution "(Creative Problem Solving) to apply this method, the beginning of the story is read How to end students, a reference is made to the judgment of students; - "cheerful riddles" (Merry Riddles) teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn words unfamiliar to them and find a thoughtful answer; - "quick answer" (Quick answers) helps to; - "Chigil wrote" ("Warm-up exercises") use of various games in the classroom to keep students interested in the lesson [3]; - "pantomime" (pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics must be explained, or when written exercises are performed and students are tired;- the "story chain" (a chain story) method helps to grow students 'oral speech; -" role-playing games " (Acting characters) To train in the profession, people in such professions as "interpreter", "Translator", "Writer", "Poet" can participate in the lesson and talk with students; - "Assembly of Allomas" (Thinkers meeting) U.Shakespeare, A.Navoi, R.Poets and writers such as Burns can be "invited". At such a moment, the use of the wise words they mentioned in the lesson helps to educate young people as perfect people; - The method" when speaking pictures " (When speaking pictures) is much more convenient and helps to teach English, to develop the oral speech of the student, students, for this it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic; - quiz cards (quiz cards) Cards are distributed depending on the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own aspects of advantage. In all such methods, cooperation between the teacher and the student, the active movement of the student in the educational process are foreseen.

Innovative tools and teaching methods are as follows: web quests, on-line training, video conferencing, open code policy ("distributed" development principle), method of specific situations, virtual reality technology.

Web search is a problematic task with elements of role-playing games, for the implementation of which the information resources of the Internet are used. The term web quest (WebQuest) was first proposed in 1995 by Bernie Dodge, Professor of educational technology at the University of SanDiego (USA). The author has developed innovative Internet programs for integration into the educational process in teaching various educational disciplines at different educational levels. Kenton Letkeman, creator of a series of educational web quests, believes that this is a "super-educational tool". a constructive approach to education is used. When performing web quests, students do not receive ready-made answers or solutions,

they independently solve the task assigned to them. Thus, working on a web quest: helps to organize active independent or group search activities; to develop creative thinking and problem-solving skills helps; allows you to implement a personal approach; teaches thinking skills (explanation, comparison, classification, general and private). Creating a web quest requires a high-level teacher with subject, methodological and information and communication skills. The topic of web quests can be the most diverse, problematic tasks may differ in the level of complexity."Bernie Dodge" describes the following tasks for web quests: [4]: retelling; planning and design; compilation; creative assignment; consensus achievement; journalistic investigation; scientific research. Based on modern requirements for university graduates, the most important tasks can be considered as creative tasks, consensus achievement, journalistic investigations, scientific research. These types of tasks for web quests allow students to fully consider the problems being studied, to present a personal attitude to the topic, which helps to strengthen the learning process. Let's consider the types of possible tasks when performing this type of web quests. The essence of the compilation task is that readers need to get information from different sources and bring it into a single format. The final compilation can be published on the Internet or presented in the form of a specific or non-digital product. For example, it can be a cookbook consisting of recipes collected on the internet, a booklet, an album containing postcards for tourists, etc. Web quests based on the puzzle task require a synthesis of information from a number of sources and create a puzzle that cannot be solved by finding a simple answer to any internet page [5]. In journalistic web quests (journalistic tasks), students must collect facts and organize them in a report, interview or other journalistic genre. A design web quest (design task) requires readers to create a product or action plan to accomplish a predetermined goal within a specific framework. For example, planning a kitchen that meets the needs of a particular family or finding a job and planning for kurgusal university graduates, among others. Creative web quests (creative products task) require students to create any product in a specific format (image, game, poster, game, song, website, multimedia presentation, etc.). Creative projects are similar in design, but their results are more free and unpredictable. Web quests for solving controversial problems (consensus building task) involve searching and presenting different, sometimes contradictory, opinions on the same problem and attempting to lead them to consensus.

A reliable web quest (persuasion task) has its own purpose, creating a product that can convince a person of something. Such a task goes beyond the usual retelling and gives readers any statement, opinion, option to solve the problem based on the materials obtained when working with a claim requires the

development of evidence for support. The final product of such a project can be a letter, an article, a press release, video recordings, a multimedia presentation, a web page, etc.

Conclusion

In conclusion, as a result of the use of innovative methods in English lessons, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes more eloquent, the skill of quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods instill in the reader a passion for knowledge. The student seeks a thorough preparation for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the education system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, competent, mature person, in the future we can add our contribution to the fact that future teachers will more perfectly develop ways to effectively use innovative technologies.

REFERENCES:

1. Jamal Jalalov foreign language 0 'methods of teaching, publishing and printing creative house 0 'teacher" Tashkent-2012
2. Bekmuratova U. B. Abstract on the topic "the use of innovative technologies in teaching English". Tashkent-2012 Year 3. Otaöoeba, M. P. The use of modern innovative technologies in teaching a foreign language and its effectiveness / m. R. Ataboeva. - Tekst: neposredstvenniy, elektronniy // Molodoy ucheniy. – 2017. – № 4.2 (138.2). - S. 36-37. - URL: 4 .<url> moluch.ru/archive/138/39058/ (data abratsheniya: 04/27/2020) N. Q. Khatamova, M.N.mirzayeva. "IN ENGLISH LESSONS 5. Interactive methods used " (methodological manual), Navoi, 2006, 40 pages.
5. M. Kholdorova, N. Feyzieva, F. Richsittilayeva. "THE USE OF AUXILIARY TOOLS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE". Tashkent: Tdpu named after Nizami, 2005
6. A'.Hashimov, I. Yagubov. "Methods of teaching English" (tutorial) Tashkent: Publishing House "Sharq", 2003